

Sharing Expertise and Experience: The Need for a Centralised Information Hub

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Creating a centralised resource to gather best practice and promote positive change regarding DRI use and development will empower people from all sectors across UKRI to make changes in their own organisations based on the most up-to-date information. The landscape in which we use DRI is constantly changing and advice is updating as we advance research and innovation in technological sustainability. We need a shared place to celebrate successes in carbon cuts and sustainability achievements and to learn from each other.

The carbon landscape is constantly changing

The fast changing carbon landscape means many of the traditional resources we use (e.g. books, academic papers) to base decisions on may already be out-of-date. Furthermore, studies taken from regions outside of the UK (e.g. the US) will not accurately reflect our own carbon landscape and therefore may not be the best basis for decision-making. An information hub would be a place that can be quickly adapted to keep up with the most up-to-date advice. Sharing ideas and advancements in one place allows us to learn from each other quickly.

Reaching people from all sectors

An information hub would help to minimise barriers to the adoption of potential efficiencies arising from new technologies in hardware and software by acting as a focal point for people from all sectors to find the information they need. The standard way of sharing new information through books and academic papers can limit findability and accessibility to an academic audience, but an information hub would be a centralised place to point people from all sectors to the most current advice and practices. Better connecting experts in technology with experts from other sectors will ensure decisions made regarding sustainable use and development of DRI can be based on expert, up-to-date advice.

Example: Heat reuse systems

Re-using excess heat generated by DRI facilities (specifically data centres) within their local communities reduces energy waste and improves carbon efficiency. Some data centres already have heat re-use in place, and this is a key example where an information hub would be a useful platform for facilities to share knowledge and best practices in this area. Furthermore, as well as practical information, a platform for facilities to share their successes and how they have overcome cost, logistical, organisational or estate related challenges can empower others to follow their example.

Provision of a centralised service to gather best practice and share the outcomes/impacts of positive changes is strongly recommended to connect advancements in sustainable DRI use across UKRI.

Supporting recommendations

A general discussion of the recommendations can be found in section 3.2 of the [Net Zero DRI Scoping Project's final technical report: Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure](#)¹. A full list of the recommendations can be found in Appendix 3 of the final report and in addition can be accessed via this [spreadsheet](#).

Recommendation 102: Share knowledge and experience of heat re-use in data centres. Engage with respondents that have heat re-use systems in place. Look for opportunities for knowledge exchange to make heat re-use into standard practice for UKRI.

Recommendation 105: Create a centralised resource to gather best practice and promote positive change. Provide a service, such as a centralised hub/group/knowledgebase, to gather best practice and share the outcomes/impacts of positive changes.

Recommendation 91: Local energy and reuse. Any practice and experience should be shared on local sources of energy and heat reuse, leading to a knowledge base on costs and opportunities.

Recommendation 94: Data centre design knowledge base. A central shared knowledge base on data centre design and best practice should be developed, with input from DRI managers, and sustained into the future with mechanisms to influence actual practice.

Recommendation 5: Blending the discipline categorisations of infrastructure and research. Steps must be taken to minimise barriers to the adoption of potential efficiencies arising from new technologies in hardware and software, e.g. ensuring adequate cross over between experts of science and experts of technology.

Recommendation 102: Share knowledge and experience of heat re-use in data centres. Engage with respondents that have heat re-use systems in place. Look for opportunities for knowledge exchange to make heat re-use into standard practice for UKRI.

Recommendation 8: Integration of DRI as part of wider estate infrastructure ... ensuring valuable outputs (e.g. heat) are integrated into institutions' estates ...

Recommendation 84: Test against best practice recommendations e.g. from PRACE. ... which include planning for ... re-use of waste heat ...

Recommendation 91: Local energy and reuse. Any practice and experience should be shared on local sources of energy and heat reuse, leading to a knowledge base on costs and opportunities.

¹ Juckes, M., Bane, M., Bulpett, J., Cartmell, K., MacFarlane, M., MacRae, M., Owen, A., Pascoe, C., & Townsend, P. (2023). Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>